

4th International Conference
DATA FOR POLICY 2019
Digital Trust and Personal Data

University College London

Main Conference: **11-12 June 2019**

Pre-Conference Workshops and

Tutorials: **10 June 2019**

#dataforpolicy2019

Welcome

It is a great honour and pleasure to welcome you all to the fourth conference of *Data for Policy*, with this year highlighting the theme of *Digital Trust and Personal Data*. The choice of this theme reflects the growing concern and public consciousness with respect to the ubiquitous adoption and utilization of new digital technologies in every aspect of daily life. Indeed, as the conference has grown, so has the normalization of these technologies and readiness to consider how questions of governance and policy can be tackled in novel ways. This year we have thirty nations represented and over a hundred presentations during the two-day proceedings. This highlights the diverse reach and global importance of the data science in policy and governance.

The 2019 program includes significant keynotes and plenary sessions and we are particularly pleased to host the UK State Minister for Digital & the Creative Industries Margot James MP, who will deliver the opening address on the UK Government's perspective. This year's conference also corresponds with the launch of the *Data & Policy* journal; a Data for Policy – Cambridge University Press collaboration. The journal fills the lacuna of policy-data interaction, bringing together academia, civil service and industry. It is vital that these communities are engaging one another. This is precisely what was intended with the Data for Policy conferences back in 2015, and the intention now with this new publication venue, *Data & Policy*.

In contrast to previous conferences, which focused on the opportunities provided by data and complex analytical methods, this year you will notice that digital ethics is a central component. This not only reflects the inherent 'ethical' motivation of governance, but also a maturing of the data science discipline and practitioner community. The stakes are high – citizen service delivery, public health, environment, policing, justice and law, social cohesion, etc. – and with this comes great responsibilities. However, it is also an exciting time and one full of possibility. I believe it is vital for us to recognize the potential of the digital transformation to overcome our historical biases and prejudices, to realize a better and fairer world.

A multi-disciplinary perspective is crucial. Bringing together a diversity of approaches, here at UCL we have recently established the *UCL Digital Ethics Forum* to explore *both* the emerging computer science theories around the issues of fairness, privacy, transparency, trust, and safety etc., and the broader humanistic issues concerning values and principles, and institutional, political, legal and social structures. One clearly cannot expect, or be expected to, tackle such major issues without stepping out of one's comfort zone! *Data for Policy* is motivated by this belief.

Data for Policy has evolved as an open initiative and I invite you all to get in touch with feedback, suggestions and collaborative ideas. I would like to sincerely thank my co-chairs and all our conference committee members, partnering institutions, and everyone here today, for their invaluable contributions. I hope you all enjoy the conference and we hope to see you next year in New York.

Zeynep Engin
Founder, Data for Policy

Committees & Partners - Many thanks to...

Conference Chairs:

Zeynep **Engin** – Data for Policy, University College London
Jon **Crowcroft** – University of Cambridge, Alan Turing Institute
Stefaan **Verhulst** – The GovLab, New York University

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C. Leigh **Anderson** – University of Washington

Chair for the Posters Session:

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Emre **Kazim** – Data for Policy & GovTech Lab, UCL

Supporting Institutions:

- University College London & GovTech Lab
- Cambridge University Press
- Office for National Statistics
- University of Cambridge
- New York University – The Government Laboratory (GovLab)
- UK Science and Innovation Network
- The Alan Turing Institute
- Imperial College London
- University of Oxford - Oxford Internet Institute
- The London School of Economics and Political Science
- European Commission
- All Party Parliamentary Group on Data Analytics, UK Parliament
- The Royal Statistical Society

Internet Access

Code Name: Data for Policy 2019

1. Connect to the UCLGuest Wireless Network.

2. Open a web browser and navigate to a page outside of UCL.

The browser will automatically redirect to the UCLGuest Welcome page.

3. Click on the link to the Self Service page; enter your information in the fields provided.

4. Click 'Generate Account'.

5. Your username and password will be displayed on the screen; these details will also be sent to your e-mail address. Make a note of your username and password as you will need them each time you log into UCLGuest (the system will not remember your login details). The details will be valid for 2 weeks as indicated by the expiry date; if the event code is valid for longer than 2 weeks you can generate another account once your current one has expired.

6. Click on the link to the Login page and enter your details. (Please be aware it may take up to 60 seconds for your account to become active after it's been generated, if you cannot log in please wait a short while and try again).

NOTE: The programme Onavo is known to prevent access to the UCLGuest Service. Onavo compresses data over 3G by proxying everything to a remote server. Please uninstall this software before attempting to connect.

Important Note: For those who wish to be excluded from published **photography and filming**, please approach a member of the team and we will provide red lanyards for identification.

Conference Timeline

Pre-Conference Workshops & Tutorials - Monday, June 10th	
08:45 - 09:15	Arrivals & Registration
09:15 - 10:45	Morning Session Part 1
10:45 - 11:05	Break
11:05 - 12:35	Morning Session Part 2
12:35 - 13:30	Lunch
13:30 - 15:00	Afternoon Session Part 1
15:00 - 15:20	Break
15:20 - 16:50	Afternoon Session Part 2
Day 1 - Tuesday, June 11th	
08:45 - 09:15	Arrivals & Registration (Tea & Coffee)
09:15 - 09:30	Welcome & Introductions
09:30 - 09:50	Opening Keynote
09:50 - 11:00	Plenary Session 1
11:00 - 11:30	Break
11:30 - 12:30	Parallel Session 1
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch Break + Posters
13:30 - 14:30	Keynote Lecture 1
14:35 - 15:35	Parallel Session 2
15:35 - 16:00	Break
16:00 - 17:00	Parallel Session 3
17:30 - 19:30	<i>Data & Policy Launch Reception</i>
Day 2 - Wednesday, June 12th	
09:00 - 09:30	Arrivals - Tea & Coffee
09:30 - 10:30	Parallel Session 4
10:30 - 11:00	Break
11:00 - 12:00	Keynote Lecture 2 & GovTech Lab Introduction
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch Break + Posters
13:00 - 14:00	Parallel Session 5
14:05 - 15:05	Parallel Session 6
15:05 - 15:35	Break
15:35 - 16:45	Plenary Session 2
16:45 - 17:00	Closing Remarks

Pre-Conference Programme (June 10th)

08:45 – 09:15 **Arrivals & Registration**

09:15 – 12:35 **Morning Workshops** (break at 10:45-11:05)

[G02] “Understanding the Data & Curation choices behind the Indicator: SDGs & LSMS-ISA Measures of Progress”; Instructor(s): Ayala **Wineman** and C. Leigh **Anderson**; University of Washington.

[G01] “Digital Ethics & Algorithm Assessment”; Instructor(s): Zeynep **Engin** (@zeynepengin) and Adriano S. **Koshiyama** (@askoshiyama); University College London (@UCL). Supported by **UCL Digital Ethics Forum**.

[MQ 101] “Data Stewardship in Action: Workshop on Making Data Collaboratives Systematic, Sustainable & Responsible”; Instructor(s): Stefaan **Verhulst** (@sverhulst), The GovLab, New York University (@thegovlab & @nyu).

12:35 – 13:30 **Lunch**

13:30 – 16:50 **Afternoon Workshops** (break at 15:00 – 15:20)

[JBR] “Introduction to Artificial Intelligence in Government”; Instructor(s): Jasmine **Grimsley** and Isabela **Breton**, Data Science Campus, Office for National Statistics, and, Barbara **Webber** – Cabinet Office.

[G01] “Big-Data for Policy Making & Digital Transformation”; Instructor(s): Francesco **Mureddu** (@muredduf), Lisbon Council, Italy (@lisboncouncil).

[G02] “Collaborating with Universities: Marriage made in heaven?”; Instructor(s): Olga **Sergushova**, Vania **Sena** and Gina Yannitell **Reinhardt**; University of Essex.

[MQ101] “Data Sharing & Data Trusts”; Instructor(s): Gefion **Thuermer** (@GefionT), Johanna **Walker**; University of Southampton (@unisouthampton), Peter **Wells** (@peterkwells); Open Data Institute (@ODIHQ), and Kieron **O’Hara**; University of Southampton.

Conference Programme (June 11th & 12th)

Tuesday, 11 June 2019

08:45 – 09:15 **Arrivals & Registration (South Cloisters)**

09:15 – 09:30 **Welcome & Introductions (Jeremy Bentham Room – JBR)**

David **Price** (@DavidPriceUCL), Vice Provost (Research), UCL (@UCL)

Zeynep **Engin** (@zeynepengin), Founder, Data for Policy (@dataforpolicy), UCL

09:30 – 09:50 **Opening Keynote**

Margot **James** MP (@margot_james_mp), UK State Minister for Digital & the Creative Industries (@DCMS)

Chair: David **Price**, Vice Provost (Research), UCL

09:50 – 11:00 **Plenary Session 1 (JBR)**

“International Perspectives”

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst** (@sverhulst), New York University (@thegovlab & @nyu).

Speakers:

Christopher **Holmes** (@LordCHolmes), House of Lords, UK
Aaron **Maniam** (@aaronmaniam), Government of Singapore
Laura Rodríguez **Mendaro** (@laura_rodriguez), Government of Uruguay
Junseok **Hwang**, Seoul National University, South Korea (@SNUnow)

11:00 – 11:30 **Break**

11:15 – 12:15 **Parallel Session 1**

Session 1a (JBR): Governance Technologies 1

Chair: Martijn **Poel**, Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, The Netherlands

[23] *“Imagining Futures – A generative scenario-based methodology to improve planning and decision-support systems for policymakers”*; Vaibhav **Dutt**, Srijan **Sil*** (@Srijansil1), Harsha **Krishna** and Bharath **Palavalli** - Fields of View, India (@fovlabs).

[29] *“Trusted Smart Statistics: how new data will change official statistics”*; Fabio

Ricciato* and Albrecht **Wirthmann** – European Commission – EUROSTAT, Luxembourg.

[48] *"A Big Data Research Roadmap for Next Generation Policy Making"*;
Francesco **Mureddu** (@muredduf) - Lisbon Council, Belgium (@lisboncouncil).

[103] *"What is the role of a data-driven public sector in the well-being of citizens?"*
- Benjamin **Welby*** (@bmwelby) and Barbara-Chiara **Ubaldi** (@BarbaraUbaldi)
- OECD, France (@OECD).

Session 1b (G01): Ethics

Chair: Quentin **Palfrey** (@qpalfrey), Harvard University, US (@futureofprivacy)

[20] *"Informational Wellbeing"*; John Michael **Thornton** - University of Cambridge (@Cambridge_Uni), UK.

[34] *"Empowering People with Informed Consent"*; Anirban **Basu** - University of Sussex, UK, Stephen **Marsh** - UOIT, Canada, Tessa **Darbyshire*** - DDB Remedy, UK, Natasha **Dwyer** - Victoria University, Australia, and Hector **Miller-Bakewell** - University of Oxford, UK.

[76] *"Automate with caution"*; Fabrizio **Scrollini** (@fscrollini) - ILDA, Uruguay (@idatosabiertos).

Session 1c (G02): Successful Uses of Data Science and AI for Public Good - 1

Chair: Tom **Smith** (@_datasmith), Office for National Statistics, UK (@DataSciCampus)

[22] *"Faster indicators of the economic health of the UK"*; Jeremy **Rowe***, Stephen **Campbell**, Arturas **Eidukas**, Ioannis **Kaloskampis**, Louisa **Nolan**, Alex Noyvirt, Daniel **Ollerenshaw**, Edward **Rowland**, Luke **Shaw** and Andrew **Sutton** - Office for National Statistics, UK (@DataSciCampus).

[40] *"Labelling and Classifying web-scraped clothing for Consumer Price Indices"*;
Hazel **Martindale***, Edward **Rowland** and Tanya **Flower** - Office for National Statistics, UK (@DataSciCampus).

[68] *"Place Based Policy and Information Micro-services"*; Ryan **Dunn** and Aleks **Bobrowska*** - Department for Work and Pensions, UK (@DWP).

Session 1d (MQ 101): Systems & Infrastructure

Chair: Nick **Davies**, HM Revenue & Customs, UK (@HMRCgovuk)

[47] *"Linking Research Entities to Industrial sector: a hybrid methodology applied to Brazil's nanotechnology sector"*; Ronaldo **Silva** - University of Rio de Janeiro and Nanobusiness Ltd, Brazil, Leonidas **Aristodemou** - University of Cambridge and The Alan Turing Institute, UK and Adriano Soares **Koshiyama*** (@askoshiyama) - University College London (@UCL) and The Alan Turing

Institute, UK (@turinginst).

[73] *"Help without crossing boundaries"*; Marta **Markiewicz***, Jakub **Mazur*** and Michał **Zgrzywa** - Objectivity, Poland.

[104] *"Big Data Test Infrastructure"*; Marco **Fichera** and Bram **De Schouwer*** - European Commission, Belgium (@EU_Commission).

12:30 – 13:30 Lunch & Posters (South Cloisters)

List of Posters

Chair: Geraint **Rees**, University College London

[27] *"What is the relationship between population growth and economic indicators extensively for States of India?"*; Jyothi **Gupta*** (@JyothiGupta) - UCL, UK (@UCL).

[42] *"How ONS balances responsibility with opportunity to create better statistics for the public benefit"*; Zoe **Bradwick**, Tomas Sanchez **Lopez***, Ruth **James** - Office for National Statistics

[81] *"Fake News and Social Media Impacts on 2018 Election in Brazil"*; José Antônio Perez Rojas Mariano **de Azevedo*** - Fundação Getulio **Vargas**, Brazil.

[83] *"Perceptions of Data Science outputs in a local authority context: the importance of emotion and context"*; Mohamed **Souare***, Jo **Bates** - University of Sheffield (@sheffielduni), UK.

[90] *"A Brief Study on the Public Opinion Shift on the 2018 Elections in Brazil"*; José Antônio Perez Rojas Mariano **de Azevedo** - Fundação Getulio **Vargas**, Brazil.

[105] *"Eliminating Bias in Automated Decision-Making Systems Used for Recruitment"*; Yvette **Pinder*** (@yvettepinder)- UCL, UK.

[121] *"A Decentralised Digital Identity Architecture"*; Geoff **Goodell*** and Tomaso **Aste** - UCL, UK.

[123] *"UNICEF Data for Children Hub in Scotland"*; Alex **Hutchison*** - The Data Lab (@DataLabScotland), UK.

13:30 – 14:30 Keynote Lecture 1 (JBR)

"Ethics of AI and Autonomous Decision Making" –
supported by **UCL Digital Ethics Forum**

Christoph **Luetge** (@chluetge), Technical University of Munich, Germany

Chair: C. Leigh **Anderson**, University of Washington (@UW)

14:35 – 15:35 Parallel Session 2

Session 2a (JBR): *"Bridging the sociotechnical divide from a policy perspective: Knowledge sharing in cybersecurity and data management in digital technologies"* - Organised by **UCL STEaPP** (@UCLSTeAPP).

Chair: Irina **Brass** (@InaBrass)- University College London (@UCL)

[55a] *"Cyber capacity building and knowledge sharing: The UK policy community's perception of the National Cyber Security Centre"*; Alex **Chung** – University College London.

[55b] *"How policy and regulations can improve Critical Infrastructure Protection Modelling and Simulations"*; Uchenna **Ani** – University College London.

[55c] *"Exercising data subjects' rights under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the Internet of Things (IoT)"*; Kruakae **Pothong** – University College London.

[55d] *"Internet of Things, Security and Governing Wicked Problems: Learning from the Paris Agreement on Climate Change"*; Feja **Lesniewska** (@FejaLesniewska) – University College London.

Session 2b (G01): Sustainability 1

Chair: Derek **Wyatt**, UK

[7] *"Bracknell Town Council's Carbon Reduction Working Group – using data to inform effective policy"*; Peter **Hill** (@Dr_Peter_Hil), St Mary's University, Twickenham (@YourStMarys).

[43] *"Using data for risk management policy – introducing the data-oriented approach into policy-making in Japan on food safety, drug safety, earthquake disaster prevention, and climate change"*; Yasushi **Sato*** - Niigata University, Keiko **Matsuo** - Japan Science and Technology Agency, and Noel **Kikuchi** - National Graduate Institute for Policy Studies.

[122] *"WHO's transformation changing generation and use of health data to drive impact of policy actions"*; Doo Hee **You***, Tina **Purnat** and Samira **Asma** - World Health Organization, Switzerland (@WHO).

Session 2c (G02): Governance Technologies 2

Chair: Innar **Liiv** (@innarliiv), Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia (@TallinnTech)

[10] *"Data-Driven Selective Recruitment for Diversity in Citizen Participation"*; Annelieke **van den Berg***, Sarah **Giest** (@sarahgiest), Sandra **Groeneveld** and Wessel **Kraaij** - Leiden University, Netherlands (@UniLeidenNews).

[26] *"The Complex Economics of Artificial Intelligence"*; Juan **Mateos-Garcia** (@JMateosGarcia) - Nesta, UK (@nesta_uk).

[33] *"The Potential of Crowdsourcing to Advance the SDGs by Fostering Local and Global Collaboration"*; Yulistina **Riyadi**, Dikara **Alkarisya*** (@dikaraalkarisya) and Deepakshi **Rawat** - UN Global Pulse, Indonesia (@UNGlobalPulse).

[54] *"Business-to-Government (B2G) Data Sharing"*; Esther **Huyer*** and Gianfranco **Cecconi** - Capgemini Invent, Netherlands (@CapgeminiInvent).

Session 2d (MQ 101): Data-Driven Policy

Chair: Jack **Tindale** (@JackTindale), Policy Connect (@Policy_Connect)

[8] *"Policy Priority Inference: A Computational Approach for the Discovery, Evaluation and Prescription of Development Strategies"*; Omar **Guerrero*** (@guerrero_oa) - UCL & The Alan Turing Institute, UK (@turinginst), and Gonzalo **Castañeda** - CIDE, Mexico.

[17] *"Geolocation for building trust in digital data, platforms, and policy"*; Agnieszka **Leszczynski*** (@agaleszczynski) - Western University, Canada (@WesternU), Peta **Mitchell** - Queensland University of Technology, Australia, and Tim **Highfield** - University of Amsterdam, Netherlands.

[49] *"Challenges of data-driven evaluation of soft policy instruments: The poverty pass"*; Sarah **Giest*** (@sarahgiest), and Jose **Miotto** - Leiden University, Netherlands (@UniLeidenNews).

[51] *"A data driven approach to transforming our population and migration statistics"*; Vicky **Field** - Office for National Statistics, UK.

15:35 - 16:00

Break

Session 3a (JBR): Privacy 1

Chair: Anil **Bharath**, Imperial College London (@imperialcollege)

[71] *"Responsibility in Personal Data Stores. Imperfections and implications for users, platforms and third parties"*; Heleen **Janssen*** (@heleenlouiseja), Jennifer **Cobbe**, Chris **Norval** and Jat **Singh** - University of Cambridge, UK (@Cambridge_Uni).

[78] *"Data protection issues in cross-border interoperability of EHRs systems withing the European Union"*; Giorgia **Bincoletto** (@GiorgiaBinco) - University of Bologna and University of Luxembourg, Italy (@uni_lu_FDEF & @unibomagazine).

[85] *"Towards Citizens' Control Over Data? Exploring Contradictory Trends in the Emerging Regulatory Environment of Personal Data"*; Arne **Hintz** (@arne_hz) - Cardiff University, UK (@cardiffuni).

[98] *"The role of technology in governance: the example of Privacy Enhancing Technologies"*; Natasha **McCarthy*** (@ntshmccrthy) and Franck **Fourniol** - The Royal Society, UK (@RoyalSociety).

Session 3b (G01): Successful Uses of Data Science and AI for Public Good - 2

Chair: Sue **Bateman**, Deputy Director, Innovation, Government Digital Service (GDS), UK

[32] (Demo) *"PropeR: Modelling multi-modal transport and service accessibility within the UK"*; Michael **Hodge*** (@Hodge_Michael), Jasmine **Latham** and Philip **Stubbings** - Office for National Statistics, UK (@DataSciCampus).

[38] *"Machine learning the images of a city and informing urban policy making"*; Lun **Liu**, Elisabete **Silva**, Haifeng **Niu*** - University of Cambridge, UK (@Cambridge_Uni), and Hui **Wang** - Tsinghua University, China (@Tsinghua_Uni).

[100] *"Data-Driven Models Could Enable Selective, Remote Emissions Inspections for Connected-Vehicles"*; H Scott **Matthews*** and Prithvi **Acharya** - Carnegie Mellon University, US.

Session 3c (G02): Data Practices, Lessons and Challenges

Chair: Bilal **Gokpinar**, University College London

[24] *"Managing Personalization-Privacy Paradox of Digital Services: A Systematic Literature Review"*; Ming-Wei **Hsu***, Glenn **Parry**, Alex **Kharlamov** - University of the West England, UK.

[36] *"Towards trusted data sharing: guidance and case studies"*; Philippa **Westbury** - Royal Academy of Engineering (@RAEngNews).

[57] *"Enacting health data governance through blockchains"*; David **Lopez*** - University of Exeter (@UniofExeter), David **Plans** - University of Exeter, Louise **Coutts** - University of Surrey, Alan **Brown** - University of Exeter, John **Collomosse** - University of Surrey, Phil **Godsiff** - University of Exeter.

Session 3d (MQ 101): Citizenship

Chair: Tom **Wilkinson**, Department for International Development, UK (@DFID_UK)

[19] *"Critical Big Data Literacy Tools – Engaging Citizens and Promoting Responsible Internet Usage"*; Ina **Sander** (@ina_abena) - Center for Advanced Internet Studies, Germany (@CAISnrw).

[39] *"Trust, Perceptions, and Effects of News Sources & Social Media"*; Chirag **Nagpal** (@nagpalchirag) - Carnegie Mellon University, USA (@LTIatCMU).

[56] *"Complex ecologies of trust in public views on personal data mining"*; Helen **Kennedy***, Robin **Steedman** - The University of Sheffield, UK (@sheffielduni), and Rhianne **Jones** - BBC, UK (@BBC).

[101] *"Me and my big data: Understanding UK citizens data literacy"*; Simeon **Yates*** (@sjyates) and Elinor **Carmi** (@Elinor_Carmi) - University of Liverpool (@waysofbeingdigi) (@meandmybigdata), Bridgette **Wessels** - University of Glasgow, Eleanor **Lockley** - Sheffield Hallam University.

17:30 – 19:30 **Data & Policy** (@data_and_policy) **Launch Reception** – sponsored by **Cambridge University Press** (@CambridgeUP)

Wednesday, 12 June 2019

09:00 – 09:30 **Tea & Coffee (South Cloisters)**

09:30 – 10:30 **Parallel Session 4**

Session 4a (JBR): Hands-on-Data: Artificial intelligence for the design of public policy in Latin America

Chair: Tom **Smith** (@_datasmith), Office for National Statistics, UK (@DataSciCampus)

[80a] *"Hands-on-Data: Description, lessons learned, and future directions of a speedy alternative to integrate artificial intelligence into the design of public policies in Latin America"*; Lucila **Berniell*** (@luberniell), Laura **Acion** (@_lacion_) and Walter **Sosa-Escudero** (@wsosaescudero) - CAF, CONICET-UBA and Fundación **Sadosky**, CONICET-UdeSA, Argentina (@funsadosky & @institcalculo).

[80b] *"Computing accessibility metrics for Argentina"*, Carlos **Sarraute** (@ch4rleston) - Grandata, Argentina (@GrandataLabs).

[80c] *"Using data science to improve public transport in the city of Córdoba (Argentina)"*; Andres **Vazquez** (@avdata99) - Municipality of Cordoba, Information Systems and Innovation, Argentina (@MuniCba).

Session 4b (G01): Governance Technologies 3

Chair: Alison **Wolf**, King's College London (@KingsCollegeLon)

[84] *"A New Generation of Flexible Public Services in Belgium: Strategy and Blueprint"*; Rink W. **Kruk** - National Geographic Institute, Belgium, Maxim Chantillon - Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium, Thomas **Tombal*** - Université de Namur, Belgium (@UNamur), Anthony **Simonofski** - Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium, and Joep **Crompvoets** - Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium.

[91] *"Data Scores as Governance: Mapping and Analysing Data Practices Across Local Government"*; Joanna **Redden**, Lina **Dencik** and Arne **Hintz*** (@arne_hz) - Cardiff University, UK (@cardiffuni).

[99] *"National Accounting with Digital Selves"*; Harald **Stieber*** - European Commission, Belgium, and Francis **Gross** - European Central Bank, DG Statistics.

Session 4c (G02): Society & Impact

Chair: Seb **Mhatre**, Department for International Development, UK (@DFID_UK)

[11] *"Aadhaar and the Social Credit System: The Governance of Personal Data in India and China"*; Ralph **Schroeder** - University of Oxford, UK (@UniofOxford).

[58] *"Interaction between Technology and Society: Evidence from Aadhaar Enabled Payment System in India"*; Ashwini **Chhatre** and Deepanshi **Bhardwaj*** -

Indian School of Business (ISB) (@ISBedu).

[77] "*Creating linked administrative datasets for research*"; Rose **Elliot*** - Office for National Statistics, Emma **Gordon** and Paul **Jackson** - UKRI ESRC (@ESRC @UKRI_News).

Session 4d (MQ 101): Data Sharing & Trust

Chair: Gabrielle **Demange**, Paris School of Economics (@PSEinfo)

[45] "*What is a data trust and what has the Open Data Institute learnt from piloting them?*"; Jack **Hardinges** and Peter **Wells*** (@peterkwells) - Open Data Institute, UK (@ODIHQ).

[63] "*Trusted Brokers?: Identifying the Challenges Facing Data Centres*"; Lauren **Thornton**, Victoria **Neumann**, Gordon **Blair***, Nigel **Davies** and John **Watkins** - Lancaster University, UK (@LancasterUni).

[120] "*Data Protection by Design: Building the foundations of trustworthy data sharing*"; Sophie **Stalla-Bourdillon**, Gefion **Thuermer*** (@GefionT), Johanna C **Walker**, and Laura **Carmichael** - University of Southampton, UK (@unisouthampton).

10:30 – 11:00 **Break**

11:00 – 12:00 **Keynote Lecture 2 (JBR)**

"How to tell when a tech is not ready for government" – supported by **GovTech Lab**

Jon **Crowcroft** (@tforworc), University of Cambridge (@Cambridge_Uni) & Alan Turing Institute (@turinginst)

Chair: Innar **Liiv** (@innarliiv), Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia (@TallinnTech)

GovTech Lab (@GovTechLab) Introduction – Tom **Wilkinson** (DFID) and **Giles Pavey** (Unilever)

12:00 – 13:00 **Lunch & Posters (South Cloisters)**

13:15 – 14:15 **Parallel Session 5**

Session 5a (JBR): Automated Decision-making

Chair: Joanna **Chataway** (@JoannaChataway), University College London (@UCL)

[12] "*The Rule of Law and Automation in Government Decision-Making*"; Monika **Zalnieriute*** (@mzalnieriute), Lyria Bennett **Moses** and George **Williams** - The University of New South Wales, Australia.

[52] *"A pipeline to reveal emerging terminology on large text datasets"*; Thanasis **Anthopoulos***, Ian **Grimstead**, Bernard **Peat**, Michael **Hosge**, Tew **Emily** and Sonia **Mazzi** - Office for National Statistics, UK.

[62] *"Algorithmic selection: a State-of-the-art"*; Quentin **Liger***, Yemi **Oviosu**, James **Eager** and Nikolas **Reschen** - Optimity Advisors, UK (@Optimity).

[82] *"Machine learning explainability in default risk analysis"*; Philippe **Bracke*** (@PhilippeBracke) - Financial Conduct Authority, UK, Anupam **Datta** - Carnegie Mellon University, USA, Carsten **Jung** - Bank of England, UK and Shayak **Sen** - Carnegie Mellon University, USA.

Session 5b (G01): Smart Cities

Chair: H. Scott **Matthews**, Carnegie Mellon University

[31] *"Will Barcelona's grassroots-led urban experimentation through the 'data commons' policy remain and be reinforced after the local elections in May 2019?"*; Igor **Calzada*** (@ICalzada) - University of Oxford, UK (@COMPAS_oxford), and Esteve **Almirall** - ESADE Business School, Spain.

[35] *"Public Sector Internet of Things Deployments: Value, Transparency, Risks and Challenges"*; Naomi **Jacobs*** (@the_ladylark), Peter **Edwards**, Caitlin **Cottrill** - University of Aberdeen, UK, Karen **Salt** - University of Nottingham, UK, and Milan **Markovic** - University of Aberdeen, UK (@aberdeenuni).

[66] *"Governing Data-Driven Innovation through the Regulatory Sandbox: Stakeholder Collaboration in the Development of Smart Cities"*; Masaru **Yarime** (@yarime)- The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong.

Session 5c (G02): Privacy 2

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst** (@sverhulst), New York University (@thegovlab & @nyu).

[16] *"Watchdogs Needed: All Hands on Deck to Protect Privacy on the Internet"*; Quentin **Palfrey** (@qpalfrey), Harvard University, United States (@futureofprivacy).

[67] *"Differential Privacy: What's all the noise about?"*; Hector **Page*** and Charlie **Cabot** - Privitar, Kobbi **Nissim** - Georgetown, US.

[39] *"Synthetic data for decision-making"*; Chaitanya **Joshi***, Ionannis **Kaliskampis**, David **Pugh**, Louisa **Nolan** - Office for National Statistics, UK.

Session 5d (MQ 101): Communities & Public Services

Chair: Daniel **Brown**, Meganexus (@MegaNexusLtd)

[53] *"Data processing, knowledge generation and the Troubled Families Programme, in pursuit of what works?"*; Lan-Ho **Man***, Ricky **Taylor** and Naomi **Knight** - Ministry of Housing Communities and Local Government, UK.

[60] *"On the challenges of using administrative data from social care: experience using a new, linked whole-population dataset"*; Matthew **Jay***, Rachel **Pearson**, Linda **Wijlaars**, Sofia **Olhede** and Ruth **Gilbert** - UCL, UK.

[92] *"Implementing algorithms in domestic abuse risk assessment: User perspectives of the critical factors in implementing an algorithmic forecasting tool to predict domestic abuse offending"*; David **Powell** - Hampshire Constabulary, UK.

14:05 – 15:05 **Parallel Session 6**

Session 6a (JBR): Successful Uses of Data Science and AI for Public Good – 3

Chair: Dave **Johnson** (@New_To_Dave), Office for National Statistics, UK

[6] *"Identifying AI talents within LinkedIn database A machine learning approach"*; Thomas **Roca** (@Thomas_Roca) - LinkedIn (@LinkedIn)

[70] (Demo) *"RIS3-MCAT – a science and technology semantic mapping platform supporting specialisation, research and innovation policy and Sustainable Development Goals roadmapping in Catalonia"*; Enric **Fuster*** (@enric_fuster) - SIRIS Academic, Spain (@sirisAcademic), Tatiana **Fernandez** - Generalitat de Catalunya, Spain, Francesco **Massucci**, Alessandro **Mosca**, Arnau **Quinquilà**, Xavier **Gimenez** and Guillem **Rull** - SIRIS Academic, Spain.

[94] *"Detecting Areas of Potential High Prevalence of Chagas in Argentina"*; Antonio Vazquez **Brust**, Tomas **Olego**, German **Rosati**, Carolina **Lang**, Guillermo **Bozzoli** - Fundación Bungey **Born**, Argentina, Diego **Weinberg** - Fundación Mundo **Sano**, Argentina, Roberto **Chuit** – Academia Nacional de Medicina, Argentina, Martin **Minnoni** and **Carlos Sarraute*** (@ch4rleston) - Grandata, Argentina (@GrandataLabs).

Session 6b (G01): Data Under the Rule of Law

Chair: Swee Leng **Harris** (@SweeLengHarris)- The Legal Education Foundation, UK (@The_LEF)

[44a] *"Existing requirements of administrative law, and the limitations of the law and of automated decision-making systems in meeting legal standards"*; Jennifer **Cobbe** (@jennifercobbe)- University of Cambridge, UK (@Cambridge_CL).

[44b] *"Potential for Data Protection Impact Assessments processes to strengthen rule of law governance of data processing"*; Swee Leng **Harris** - The Legal Education Foundation, UK.

[44c] *"Lessons from her expert report to HMCTS on data in the digital courts system"*; Natalie **Byrom** (@NatalieByrom) - The Legal Education Foundation, UK.

Session 6c (G02): Data for Cities and the Built Environment: What role for the stakeholders?

Chair: Jennifer **Schooling** (@JenniferCSIC) - University of Cambridge

[61a] *"Building data quality in a built environment – Strategies how real estate owners could use BIM"*; Christoph **Ebbing** - Technical University of Dortmund, Germany (@TU_Dortmund).

[61b] *"Evidence-informed decision-making in multi-stakeholder settings: The case of city digital twins for planning and management"*; Timea **Nochta*** (@tnochta) and Nicole **Badstuber** - University of Cambridge, Centre for Smart Infrastructure and Construction, UK (@CSIC_IKC & @Cambridge_CDBB).

[61c] *"Digitization of German City Planning - Incentives for Comparison with UK's Planning Practice"*; Dimitri **Ravin** (@urbandigitalDE)- Technical University of Dortmund, Germany.

[61d] *"Future cities in the making - overcoming barriers to information modelling in socially responsible cities"*; Franziska **Sielker*** (@FSielker), and Amarynth **Sichel** - University of Cambridge, Department of Land Economy, UK (@CambridgeLandEc).

Session 6d (MQ 101): Sustainability 2

Chair: Stef **Garasto**, Nesta (@nesta_uk)

1. [46] *"Transparency and Openness in Food Safety: insights about new Data Confidentiality rules"*; Salvatore **Sapienza** (@salvosapie) - University of Bologna - CIRSFID, University of Luxembourg - FDEF, Italy (@unibomagazine & @uni_lu_FDEF).

[69] *"Managing sensitive data for public information: a use cases review of the French water information system"*; Alexandre Bj **Liccardi*** and Laurent **Coudercy** - AFB (French Biodiversity Agency), France.

[79] *"Definitions of "rural" and understandings of transformation in sub-Saharan Africa"*; Ayala **Wineman**, Didier Yélognissè **Alia** and C. Leigh **Anderson*** - University of Washington, USA.

15:05 – 15:35

Break

15:35 – 16:45 Plenary Session (JBR)

“Sustainable Innovation in the Public/Government Sector” –
supported by **UCL Digital Ethics Forum**

Chair: Barbara **Ubaldi** (@BarbaraUbaldi), OECD, Paris (@OECD)

Speakers:

Diego **Kuonen** (@DiegoKuonen), Universite de Geneve, Switzerland
Julia **Stoyanovich** (@stoyanoj), New York University (@NYUTandon &
@NYUDataScience,
Nicholas **Wright** (@nicholasdwright), UCL and Georgetown University
(@Georgetown)
Natasha **McCarthy** (@ntshmcrrthy), The Royal Society, UK (@RoyalSociety)
Lee **Rowley** MP (@Lee4NED) All Party Parliamentary Group on Data Analytics,
UK (@DataAPG)

16:45 – 17:00 Closing Remarks (JBR)

Lee **Rowley** MP (@Lee4NED), All Party Parliamentary Group on Data Analytics
Stefaan **Verhulst** (@sverhulst), GovLab, New York University
Zeynep **Engin** (@zeynepengin), UCL and Data for Policy

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